

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D4.2 – EU-wide INTEGER innovative community constituted

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The *Deliverable 4.2 - EU-wide INTEGER innovative community constituted* aims to document the creation of the INTEGER community, which seeks to generate and promote existing synergies, as well as raising awareness about the need to create a Europe-wide col-laboratory.

EU INTEGER Col-laboratory is an innovative concept co-created within the INTEGER project dedicated to the next generation of quadruple or n-helix living laboratories (or living labs). The seed of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory, among others, grew thanks to the activities of the Col-laboratory Catalunya and the actions carried out at regional level promoted and devised between the Generalitat de Catalunya and Fundació i2CAT. These are real-life environments where co-creation, rapid prototyping, and innovation testing take place, with a strong emphasis on the promotion of collaboration among stakeholders. In the case of INTEGER, these stakeholders come from the quadruple helix: academia, government, industry, and social organisations & citizens, addressing the several layers of the social ecosystems and interconnecting them, at a regional and transnational level.

The aim of WP4 is to develop sustainable, inclusive, and efficient initiatives and processes that establish the INTEGER 4H model, both in theory and practice. This model has been tested in regional innovation ecosystems, and a community involving regional and transnational actors will be created, with the goal of transferring the INTEGER experience to Europe and beyond.

The need to create an innovative ecosystem model arises from a huge European challenge: while numerous initiatives aim to innovate, many fail to reach the market and attract investment. Despite the abundance of labs and innovation efforts, there is a lack of networks and capacity to generate significant impact in a sustainable way. The INTEGER project aims to address this challenge by providing a sustainable model that can serve the wider ecosystem beyond its two-year duration. One of the key innovative elements of the project is thus the establishment of an EU-wide community. The second aim is linked with the WP4 actions dedicated to deploying the EU Healthy Living Col-laboratory, a network of networks designed to address real-world social, technological, and business needs and challenges.

This deliverable provides detailed information on the establishment of the EU-wide INTEGER innovative community, including the strategies and criteria for participation. It will also highlight the engagement of the 'col-labers' or 'col-laboratory managers' as catalysts for change within these integrated innovation ecosystems and underscore the importance of community feedback and its integration into project development.

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AHA	Active Healthy Ageing
AI	Artificial Intelligence
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
ESSI	European School of Social Innovation
EU	European Union
HIP	Health Innovation Port
IFB	Investment Bank Hamburg
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
KLL	Krakov Living Lab
KTP	Krakov Technology Park
UMWM	Marshal Office of the Malopolska Region
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
SIG	Special Interest Group
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
T	Task
ToR	Terms of Reference
WP	Work-Package
4H	Quadruple Helix

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

The concept of social innovation refers to new strategies, concepts, and organizations that respond to various social needs. These innovations not only develop and strengthen civil society, but also empower communities to proactively address common issues through collective problem-solving. In the sphere of social innovations, communities take charge of resolving their challenges, often giving rise to alternative economic models, distinct from the prevailing ones, without necessarily involving financial transactions [1] [2].

The successful integration of quadruple helix (4H) players, including academia, government, industry, and civil society is essential for society actors to collaboratively work towards innovation (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Quadruple helix players.

The INTEGER community attempts to foster a more inclusive and successful society by connecting social innovations that address diverse needs, ranging from working conditions and education to community development and health.

To achieve effective integration among the different actors in the ecosystem, the partners have identified three key steps to be followed throughout the course of the project:

- **Narrative building:** where initiatives build a compelling story that emphasises the significance of the cause for each stakeholder group.
- **Common ground:** it entails identifying areas of convergence among the diverse actors and fostering constructive dialogue.
- **Allocation of responsibilities:** sharing the burden and the benefits among the parties involved.

By addressing these aspects and embracing a co-creation process with stakeholders from the 4H, a more cohesive and collaborative effort can be achieved in bringing together academia, government, industry, and civil society. This approach will not only align these sectors towards a common goal but also amplify the overall impact.

Following these steps, the INTEGER community attempts to promote a more inclusive and successful society by connecting social innovations/innovators that address diverse needs, ranging from working conditions and education to community development and health.

This deliverable explains the process of creation and development of the EU-wide INTEGER innovative community, shedding light on how these efforts align with the broader goal of fostering social innovation on a European scale and how the quadruple-helix actors have been building and reinforcing connections throughout the project with a sustainable vision, beyond the project lifetime.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The *Deliverable - 4.2 EU-wide INTEGER innovative community constituted* is led by SHINE 2Europe and is based on the activities of *Task 4.3 - Deployment and Sustainability of the EU Healthy Living Col-laboratory*. Specifically, it is connected to Task 4.3.1, which involves the constitution of an EU-wide INTEGER innovative community to generate synergies and raise awareness about the need for a Europe-wide col-laboratory. This deliverable is part of the *Work Package 4 - INTEGER 4H Model & EU Healthy Living Col-laboratory Deployment*, led by i2CAT, which aims to develop sustainable, inclusive, and efficient initiatives and processes that establish the INTEGER 4H model both in theory and practice. This model will be tested in regional innovation ecosystems, and a community involving regional and transnational actors will be created to transfer the INTEGER experience to Europe and beyond.

This deliverable describes the process behind creating the EU-wide INTEGER innovative community, highlighting its importance and sustainability. It presents a methodology supported by a systemic design that details the activities undertaken to establish and maintain the community throughout the project's duration. Additionally, it includes plans for ongoing efforts to sustain and advance the model and the community beyond the project's completion. The aim is to foster and engage quadruple-helix stakeholders within each regional innovation ecosystem and across Europe, ensuring the community's long-term sustainability.

In that sense, this deliverable is divided into five chapters: the **first chapter** introduces the content and outlines the synergies with other tasks and deliverables; the **second chapter** explains the need for creating an EU-wide INTEGER innovative community and details the steps taken, including the regional Col-laboratories, the *Glocal platform*, and the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory of Health and Wellbeing; **chapter three** describes the methodology for establishing this community and the supporting activities; the **fourth chapter** presents the sustainability plan for the community; and **chapter five** provides the conclusions.

1.3 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

Both WP2 and WP3 provide the foundation for developing the model for the col-laboratory and play a crucial role in informing and engaging stakeholders to join the EU-wide innovative community for health and well-being (see Figure 2). WP5, which focuses on dissemination and stakeholder mapping and engagement, is also closely connected to this effort, as diverse stakeholders were invited to join this European community.

Figure 2 – Connections between WP4, WP2 and WP3.

Both WP2 and WP3 provide the foundation for the model development of the col-laboratory and they play a crucial role in supporting the engagement of stakeholders to join the EU-wide innovative community for health and well-being (see Figure 2). WP5, focuses on dissemination and stakeholders mapping and engagement, is also closely connected to this effort, as diverse stakeholders were reached through dissemination and communication efforts, namely invited to join this European community, in the *Glocal.network platform*.

The synergies with other tasks and deliverables are also explained in Table 1.

Table 1 - WPs, Tasks and Deliverables related to D4.2

WP	TASK	DELIVERABLE	DUE DATE
WP2 – LEARNING FOR COL-LABORATORY CO-DESIGN	Task 2.1 Establish digital co-creation environments (the digital platform) for Best Practices Exchange	D2.3 INTEGER Platform guidelines D2.4 Report on inter-ecosystem projects and best practices exchanged	Delivered Delivered
	Task 2.2 Reinforce inter-ecosystem 3H & 4H dynamics between social entrepreneurs and	D2.1 Inter-ecosystem hands-on visits plan	Delivered

	stakeholders in each innovation ecosystem		
	Task 2.3 European-wide Col.laborathon organisation and implementation	D2.2 Col.laborathon Report & Exploitation Plan	Delivered
	Task 2.4 Col.laborathon results exploitation	–	–
WP3 – CO-CREATION OF EU HEALTHY LIVING COL-LABORATORY	Task 3.1 Co-creation digital arenas for capacity building among innovator actors in the three regions with a twofold axis: a) Bringing attention to the benefits of social innovation projects to the society through capacity building, b) Developing business support services for social entrepreneurs (templates, manuals and other support material)	D3.1 Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and training pills delivery (I)	Delivered
		D3.2 Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and training pills delivery (II)	Delivered
		D3.3 Report on main features of the 3 regional Innovation Ecosystem Models	Delivered
	Task 3.2 Organisation and implementation of one Col.laborathon in each region to pilot the incubation and acceleration of selected social projects using the INTEGER col·laboratory methodology, with special focus on the technology and business strategy support to individual projects	D3.4 Three (3) Col.laborathons Final Reports	Delivered
Task 3.3 Piloting the incubation and acceleration of selected social-digital projects via regional Col.laborathons	D3.5 Business support intermediate services portfolio D3.6 Regionalised Incubation and Acceleration Report	Delivered M24	
WP4 – INTEGER 4H MODEL & EU HEALTHY LIVING COL-LABORATORY DEPLOYMENT	Task 4.1 Gathering and systematisation of relevant information and material in the INTEGER platform hub	–	–
	Task 4.2 Development of a comprehensive model to accelerate the integration and	D4.1 First draft of comprehensive 3H & 4H integration	Delivered

	collaboration of social innovation actors and digital business entrepreneurial hubs	innovation ecosystems model D4.3 INTEGER 4H col-laboratory comprehensive model: academic papers accepted in scientific publications	M22
	Task 4.4 Interconnecting and exchanging with the related initiatives, networks, communities and projects	D4.4 Report on coordination actions with key related initiatives	M24
WP5 – ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION	Task 5.1 Communication and dissemination plan and activities	D5.1 Communication, dissemination and stakeholders’ engagement plan	Delivered
	Task 5.2 Stakeholder engagement and liaison with relevant initiatives	D5.2 Stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives and impact monitoring report	M24
	Task 5.3 Impact monitoring and maximisation plan and activities	D5.3 Communication, dissemination, and stakeholders’ implementation report	M24

2 EU-wide INTEGER innovative community

Statistics show that there are approximately 2 million social economy enterprises in Europe, representing 10% of all businesses in the EU. More than 11 million people—about 6% of the EU's employees - work for social economy enterprises [3]. Nearly one in four businesses founded in Europe is a social enterprise. Achieving the green and digital transitions requires a significant effort to include social economy enterprises, social innovators, and entrepreneurs more decisively in our EU innovation ecosystems. This is where the quadruple helix model [3] comes into play.

However, effectively managing the diverse needs of these different stakeholders can be quite challenging and requires an innovative strategy. Until the 1990s, the basic premise underpinning most national innovation systems was that scientific findings and inventions would naturally lead to economic development and societal advancement. The Research and Development community drove research trajectories in basic, applied, and industrial research, with the public as passive recipients of innovation.

Over the last three decades, a new approach has gained prominence. Research trajectories must be legitimised among relevant publics, aiming for positive public impact, and be defined with public input & feedback. The expectation is that by involving societal stakeholders and citizens it helps to re-align and improve research trajectories with public preferences, leading to more welcome and sustainable solutions [4].

The INTEGER EU-wide innovative community aims to close the gap between different sectors, bringing together stakeholders (social innovators) from the quadruple helix to create a collaborative laboratory focused on health and wellbeing. Initially aiming at regional innovation ecosystems in Catalonia, Hamburg, and Krakow, the community has expanded across various European regions and international environments. This widening of the ecosystem aimed to promote transnational exchanges and establish the INTEGER model as a foundation for challenge-driven thematic partnerships.

During the INTEGER project, various initiatives were developed to form and consolidate this community:

- The first activities included **regional study visits**, organised as three experimental Col-laboratories. These events took place both in-person and in hybrid formats across Catalonia, Hamburg, and Krakow. Its results are reported in *Deliverable 3.3*.
- An **online pre-event** and **2 sessions of the model event** gathered key stakeholders from the 4 helixes identified by the INTEGER partners, from the 3 Regional Col-laboratories. These events aimed to promote reflection and collect inputs on the challenges and needs of the three different regions and also identify common challenges. These outputs would support the topics developed in the following stages of the col-laboration initiatives (WP2).
- One other initiative was the implementation and adaptation of an innovative digital tool with the objective to connect all community members online to promote regional and

interregional actions: the **Glocal.network** platform <https://integer4h.theglocal.network>, explained in *Deliverable 2.3*.

- The final activity was the engagement of stakeholders in different channels, events (online, face-to-face and hybrid) and initiatives, consolidated by the invitation to endorse a formal document – Terms of Reference – to strengthen their commitment.

Step 1: The Regional Col-laboratories

The establishment of this EU-wide community began by connecting various regional col-laboratories and has since expanded to a broader EU-wide framework. Initially, three col-laboratories were established within the regional ecosystems of Catalonia, Hamburg, and Krakow. These interactions demonstrated how embracing the quadruple helix model, fostering a collaborative ethos, and engaging a diverse range of stakeholders contribute to the growth of innovation ecosystems. As INTEGER progresses in its mission to support regional quadruple helix ecosystems, the early visits to each regional innovation ecosystem provided valuable insights and lessons that have informed and guided the subsequent phases of the project work plan.

Step 2: The Glocal.network Platform

To establish and sustain the EU-wide INTEGER innovative community, having an effective communication and collaboration tool was crucial. A digital platform was identified as a potential solution for this need. The INTEGER project proposed making the best use of this digital platform, known as the *Glocal.network*: theglocal.network.

This platform is designed to build a community across diverse geographical locations, providing a space for participants from various fields - such as government, civil society, industry, and academia - to connect and collaborate. The platform intends also to align with participants' interests and facilitate their future collaborations and successes.

The INTEGER project's regional and interregional activities actively encourage logins, sign-ins, and interactions through the digital community platform. Increasing the amount of content, communication, and project activities shared on the platform will help to generate interest, enhance community engagement, and boost visits and knowledge sharing.

This platform features the "**Col-laber Corner**" (<https://theglocal.network/ideas/facilitators-corner>), a section that, since March 2024, serves as a repository of materials exploring the role of the Col-laber within the community platform. It offers users a way to understand the importance of the Col-laber's role and includes the Col-laber Curriculum with 13 video tutorials, a recording of the Col-laber Training Day, and a recording of the Incubation Training: "How to Sell with AI".

The new section, "**Learning Network**", is an ongoing development tool to be launched in September 2024. This platform serves as a central hub for sharing research, discovering new opportunities, and finding digital solutions in the field of social innovation related to health and

well-being across Europe and the world. To facilitate this, a chat section will be available, allowing participants to answer prompted questions or submit their own for community feedback. Additionally, various resources such as documents, news, articles, papers, and websites will be accessible to all participants. These resources will cover research, new opportunities, and digital solutions and tools related to health and well-being to support the stakeholder's best interest.

Step 3: The EU INTEGER Col-laboratory of Health and Wellbeing

The EU INTEGER Col-laboratory for Health and Wellbeing is an officially established and agile framework designed to foster collaboration and drive innovation among partners from the quadruple helix. This framework aimed to create robust and interconnected innovation ecosystems that aligned with the triple transition objectives: social, ecological, and digital.

The UE INTEGER Col-laboratory concept is formalised through the signing of a membership form¹ and terms of reference agreement² and includes five key breakthrough innovations for integrating social innovation into European innovation ecosystems:

1. **Fostering win-win dynamics:** Promotes mutually beneficial outcomes by linking business and social innovations to effectively address common challenges.
2. **Translating co-creation into tangible results:** Focuses on transforming collaborative efforts into new, disruptive products, services, or competencies.
3. **Co-designing public innovation policies:** Involves the joint development of innovative public policies to drive sector-wide progress.
4. **Developing training programs:** Prepares the next generation of socio-digital entrepreneurs and facilitators, known as 'col-labers,' to enhance innovation ecosystems.
5. **Establishing funding mechanisms:** Creates strategies to support social innovation start-ups and SMEs, aiding in the expansion of their innovative capacities.

As mentioned, participation in the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory requires individuals and organisations to sign the terms of reference agreement, which formalises their involvement. The Col-laboratory operates as a bidirectional channel, allowing members to communicate their needs and request support from INTEGER. Additionally, members are encouraged to share updates and advancements, using the Glocal.network platform, thereby promoting the integration of project results within their organisations and fostering a broader dissemination

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EUINTEGERCollaboratorySurvey2024>

² <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WYAI5Nkyxz5yZO8fAfM0wY4thX9zpFLN/view>

and impact of the project's outcomes. In that sense, the EU-wide INTEGER innovative community can be represented in the infographic below:

Figure 3 - INTEGER EU-wide innovative community

The next chapter will explain the methodology behind the creation of this community and how it was addressed in the different phases of the project.

3 Methodology for the constitution of an EU-wide INTEGER innovative community

Integrating quadruple helix stakeholders, each with distinct needs even if towards a shared objective, may be complex and uncertain. INTEGER regional col-laboratories must function effectively while also enhancing their collaboration with transnational initiatives, fostering a cohesive EU-wide community. Collaborative and multi-stakeholder processes take time and designing them requires more than a single meeting or workshop. These processes need to be flexible to accommodate an emergent learning process while still providing a roadmap of desired and feasible sequential outcomes for those tasked with managing them [5, 6].

Figure 4 - Scheme of EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Wellbeing

In Figure 4, the regional Col-laboratory is illustrated on the left by the three regional innovation ecosystems: Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia, depicted in blue, green, and orange, respectively. On the right, there is the EU-wide Col-laboratory, which not only includes these three regional ecosystems but also incorporates additional stakeholders from the 4H, represented in red.

Regional activities aim to build strong, relevant relationships among 4H actors within each region, providing a location and contextualised setting [8]. Meanwhile, interactions between regions are encouraged through transnational events to foster EU-wide collaborations. This

systemic approach of "zooming in and zooming out" supports the community's development and integrate diverse views.

These activities align with the phases illustrated in Figure 5. Initially, efforts focused on scanning the environment to gather information and understand the challenges within each regional innovation ecosystem. Followed by the analysis and discussion of shared challenges in regional and interregional workshops. Following this, prototypes began to be tested through the launch of the INTEGER Co·laboratory, regional and interregional col·laborathons, supported by the use of the INTEGER platform that promotes continued communication among different stakeholders and regions. Currently, the community is in the evaluation and reflection phase, assessing lessons learned and identifying areas for improvement that will enable a plan for growth and strengthening the community.

Additionally, communication and dissemination efforts have been undertaken to generate interest in project activities and reach a broader audience. These efforts have utilised a variety of channels, including social media posts, updates on the project website, conferences, and more. Further details are provided in Section 3.4.

Recognizing the large number and diversity of stakeholders in the regional innovation ecosystems across Europe, as well as the complexity of engaging them in an EU-wide community, was essential in adopting a systemic design framework. This comprehensive approach considers all parts, their interconnectedness and utilises methods suited to navigating the complexity involved in establishing an innovative EU-wide community [5,6].

Systemic design Labs [4] define Systemic Design as “approaching a task from a holistic perspective, zooming out of a system to reveal its structure and connections between its parts – to zoom in on the hub of influence that matters most”. The Co.Lab’s Systemic Design methodology [7] was employed to conceptualise and describe the INTEGER EU-wide community. This approach helped the partners to guide collaborative work through four interrelated phases, recognising that creating an innovative community is a complex and non-linear process. The phases are (Figure 5):

Figure 5 – Col.Lab's Systemic Design methodology

When considering how to create an EU-wide INTEGER innovative community focused on health and well-being, several key questions arose:

- Who should be included in this community?
- How can communication between different participants be fostered?
- How can participants' engagement be increased and collaborations between actors from the 4H be encouraged?
- How can an EU-wide community on Health and Wellbeing sustain over the project duration?

The following sections will address these questions, outlining the rationale behind the establishment of the EU-wide INTEGER innovative community and detailing the various activities.

3.1 Scan the environment and organisation for information and experience

The initial phase in establishing the EU-wide community involved identifying 4H stakeholders suitable for integration into each regional innovation ecosystem (Catalonia, Krakow, and Hamburg) and across Europe. To gain insights into this environment, study visits were conducted within each regional innovation ecosystem, complemented by consultations with living labs.

Mapping stakeholders

The first step involved mapping relevant stakeholders and creating an engagement plan from the quadruple helix related to health and well-being (*Deliverable 5.1 - Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholders' Engagement Plan*). **33 stakeholders** were identified from the 3 regional innovation ecosystems in the INTEGER project and relevant stakeholders at an international level (see Annex 1). These were contacted for upcoming events.

Living labs

27 Living Labs in health and well-being from regions of INTEGER participant consortiums and other European locations were contacted and participated in project activities. Some of the Living Labs involved are based in Spain, Germany and Poland, and include Col-laboratory Catalunya, LivingLab Irsi Caixa, EcoRegio Living Lab, DynamisLab, Cluster Saude, Ambit Interiors Living Lab, SeniorLab, SmartCentre, FarmLab, ActivaLab, LABORA, LaboraLab, LL4CC Living Labs for Climate Change, CareCityLab, VallsGenera, Neàpolis Lab, BALL, SuaraLab, LISD VIC Digital Social Innovation Lab, Fundació Èpica Lab, FIRE-RES LLab, HCLLC Health Care Living Lab, Coboilab, Leibnitz Living Lab, PraxLabs University, and Kraków LifeScience Cluster.

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), based in Brussels, was also involved in this process. Through ENoLL, INTEGER has access to a broad network of stakeholders and resources, enhancing collaboration and innovation, which is particularly relevant to the project aims.

Specific characteristics of the three regional innovation ecosystems

It is important to note that activities within the three regional innovation ecosystems have been tailored to their specific characteristics. To better understand these distinctions, here is a concise overview of each ecosystem's unique context:

- **Catalonia** (Spain)

The Col-laboratory Catalunya was launched in 2018, by i2CAT and with the support of the Catalan Government. This structured approach has facilitated organised efforts in regional innovation. Since 2015 a unit of social innovators has connected i2CAT with a broader regional and European social entrepreneur community. The Catalan Col-laboratory Catalunya program is now a well-established initiative of the Catalan Directorate General of Digital Society integrating 3H and 4H models based on the use of advanced digital technologies to generate a universal innovation ecosystem in the region. The program now includes five territorial col-laboratories (CatSud, Anoia, CatNord, CatPonent-Pirineus, CatAreaMetropolitana) and two thematic ones (Health and Wellbeing and Education). The regional Col-laboratory Catalunya on Health and Wellbeing includes advanced health research centres like ISGlobal or IRSI-Caixa, the Foundation TIC Salut, the Catalan Health unit dealing with ICT policies, the municipalities of Mataró, Igualada, Vic and Vilanova i la Geltrú, communities of makers and fablabs like Malla, or Biocat, the organisation that promote the Bioregional ecosystem of Catalonia. In summary, the Col-laboratory community is showing that integration of social innovation actors into the regional innovation ecosystems is possible and beneficial, resulting in new opportunities identification and potential developments with social impact.

- **Krakow** (Poland)

The pilot region of Krakow is also presenting established collaborations that get monitored within the INTEGER project. The Krakow Living Lab (KLL) serves as the platform for testing innovative products and services in public environments. The open ecosystem involves hundreds of varied multi-stakeholders bringing and sharing experience and know-how on dimensions such as social innovation, innovation management, cooperation and co-creation between start-ups/SME and large enterprises, incubation and acceleration programmes, approaches to innovation (examples: Living Lab, design thinking, hackathons), branch events, product development and more. It serves as a hub for main innovation actors including public institutions, researchers (like universities), technology and knowledge transfer institutions and end-users. KLL is a joint venture of the Krakow Technology Park (KTP), which provides a business perspective and is involved in various incubation and acceleration programs. The Jagiellonian University represents academia within the regional ecosystem.

- **Hamburg** (Germany)

The innovation ecosystem of Hamburg involves several institutions. For instance, the Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH (GWHH) acts as a cluster agency for the health economy, maintaining a network of over 3,000 decision-makers. A further governmental player is the Investment Bank Hamburg (IFB) which supports innovation through business development assistance and funding schemes. Additionally, the Health Innovation Port (HIP) of Phillips provides a collaboration space, incubator, accelerator, and knowledge platform, promoting cooperation between science and business.

Study visits

Study visits took place in the 3 regions: Catalonia (February 15, 2023); Krakow (March 28-29, 2023); and Hamburg (March 30-31, 2023). These visits highlighted collaborative efforts to address health and well-being challenges through the 4 Helix model, benefiting from the unique opportunities and challenges in each of the regions. Detailed information from these visits is available in *Deliverable 2.1 INTEGER-Inter-ecosystem hands-on visits plan* and in *Deliverable 3.3 - Report on main features of the 3 Regional Innovation Ecosystem Models*.

Catalonia workshops were focused on stakeholder engagement to address ageing issues and integrated care. There were **60 attendees** for this study visit, most of them Catalan stakeholders, but also the INTEGER partners representing the stakeholders from the regions of Hamburg and Krakow.

Krakow sessions emphasised the alignment of social and business innovators and addressed implementation challenges. A co-creation workshop was conducted with around **25 attendees**. There have been many distinguished guests: representatives of companies and startups (FindAir and Parenting Technologies), NGOs (Internationaler Bund Polska, Saint Albert Foundation), clusters (Cluster Life Science Krakow), and universities (Jagiellonian University).

Hamburg highlighted the role of startups and innovative technologies in healthcare. An engagement with Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH (GWHH), the cluster agency for the health economy owned by Hamburg's Chamber of Commerce and the Ministry of Social affairs took place. It is an important promoter in the healthcare sector with a network of about 3.000 members. 20 **individuals** participated in this study visit.

Figure 6 - From top left to bottom right: regional study visits in Catalonia, Krakow, and Hamburg.

The study visits helped as well to increase the stakeholders' interest in joining the Glocal.network platform of INTEGER achieving after the first year of the project nearly 140 registered members from different EU regions.

3.2 Build shared challenges and actions

Regional and interregional workshops and co-creation sessions were conducted to initiate two key objectives:

1. Establishing shared challenges and actions within each regional context.
2. Fostering cohesion and collaboration across regional innovation ecosystems.

The following sections detail the specific actions undertaken to strengthen community ties within each regional innovation ecosystem and across borders.

Informative sessions

To strengthen regional relationships and partnerships within regional innovation ecosystems—seen as essential for building a community across shared challenges and actions—regional meetings and co-creation sessions have been held in Catalonia, Krakow and Hamburg. The regional innovation ecosystems have approached workshops and sessions in various ways, reflecting their unique characteristics and stages of development, as mentioned before. This information is fully detailed in *Deliverable 2.1 INTEGER-Inter-ecosystem hands-on visits plan*.

In **Catalonia**, the **first information and co-creation session** took place before the beginning of the INTEGER project, at the i2CAT Foundation offices on December 13, 2022. Potential stakeholders, some of whom had already been participating in the Catalonia Col-laboratory for about a year, were invited. Approximately 120 people were invited, and **46 attended** the session in person.

A **second information session was held online** on February 2, 2023, for those who could not attend the previous physical session. This session focused on explaining the INTEGER project and encouraging more organisations to participate through the Letter of Interest. Of the 74 people invited, **39 attended**.

In total, **85 people from various 4 Helix organisations** attended the two information sessions, resulting in 49 signed Expressions of Interest—27 in paper format and 22 digitally.

In **Krakow**, it was decided to form the **focus group** that is vital for the presented model and can provide business continuity when the INTEGER project is over. Thanks to the cooperation created among key stakeholders representing local, regional and national public administration, technology transfer centres, universities, Municipal Social Welfare Centre and Regional Social Welfare Centre and the NGOs focused on social innovation, the consortium has been able to upgrade the existing model of collaboration with vital insights from our stakeholders. In addition to that, the Krakow team invited the listed above representatives of various 4 Helix organisations to take part in a meeting with the **Special Interest Group (SIG)** on the theme of Active Healthy Ageing (AHA) organised together with Life Science Cluster in Krakow. During their main event actors from quadruple helix were engaged, to get their feedback regarding the project and the model. Following the first initial meeting held on 30th November 2023. The SIG meeting on 30th November was focused on the discussion on the collaborative model and how the cooperation of key regional stakeholders should look to create and maintain business continuity of a new generation of Living-Labs for health and quality of life. The agenda of the SIG meeting covered among others such topics as INTEGER as an example of creating a new generation of laboratories – bridging the cooperation of the social and technology innovators and investors. The second part of the meeting was focused on Local challenges, international solutions – experiences of Krakow and the region in creating an innovation ecosystem to end with a co-creation workshop on the INTEGER 4Helix cooperation model and col.laboratory model discussion and recommendations on how to improve the model led by KPT team.

The **second meeting of the Special Interest Group** was organised on 14th February 2024 to discuss scope of potential cooperation within actors and get approval of the evaluation criteria for innovative projects submitted under the competitions of the Malopolska Regional

Operational Program. These criteria were included in the Specialization Annex for Smart Specialization of Life Sciences, which was updated and submitted to the Marshal Office of the Malopolska Region (UMWM) by the end of February, with feedback and reflection provided by the Krakow team. The second part of the SIG meeting was focused on the presentation and discussion of the goals and action plans of SIG AHA in 2024 in the context of the new AHA Innovation Accelerator program implemented in cooperation with the Marshal Office of the Malopolska Region and co-financed within the EIT Health Hub.

In total, **28 people from various 4 Helix organisations attended both meetings**. Moreover, they submitted their interest in further cooperation by accessing the AHA database led by the Life Science Cluster in Krakow. The AHA Special Interest Group (SIG) meetings are organised on a regular basis every 3-4 months. The Krakow team is taking part in the SIG meetings.

Figure 7 - Special Interest Group in Krakow

Figure 8 – Methodology for the Special Interest Group in Krakow

Figure 9 - Recommendation to Col-laboratory Model by SIG in Krakow

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In **Hamburg**, a **working meeting** was held on April 25, 2023, with Mr. Alexander Fischer, the managing director of INVEST Billstedt/Horn, at the Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs, counting **4 participants**. The discussion centred on a prototype for integrated full health care in deprived

metropolitan regions. The Billstedt and Mümmelmannsberg health kiosks represent an innovative approach to neighbourhood-based healthcare in Hamburg, focusing on developing patient-centred care structures and processes and testing new digital applications to improve communication between doctors and patients.

Complementary to those activities, a **stakeholder workshop** took place on January 26, 2024, in Hamburg's regional ecosystem, with **8 participants**. Kai Schnackenberg presented previous project results and feedback, as HAM representative in the INTEGER project. Silke Betscher and Anna Köster-Eisenfunke provided background on their project, “Community Health – Gesundheit und Wohnen auf der Veddel”, participatory elements in care, and relevant social determinants. A possible Hamburg Living Lab was discussed for the Veddel district³, along with knowledge transfer to other local health centres. The workshop identified cooperation structures for the Veddel district, pending negotiations with national health insurance companies to determine the funding model.

Interregional Co-Creation sessions and workshops

To promote the use of the collaborative INTEGER platform, foster a culture of openness, encourage cross-sector partnerships and initiatives towards social innovation, and enhance stakeholder engagement across the three regional innovation ecosystems, co-creation sessions and workshops have been organised. These interregional events bring together participants from all three regions, facilitating collaboration and idea-sharing. All the details from these events are in *Deliverable 2.2 - Col-laborathon Report & Exploitation Plan*.

It has been important the identification of champions and early adopters, stakeholders with the vision aligned with INTEGER (systemic transformation). Thanks to it a task force group was formed to define and refine the INTEGER methodology model, ensuring its alignment with project objectives. Various initiatives and events were organised, including working sessions and events together with INTEGER partners and key stakeholders, the formation of a Model Core Group on the platform named “Model Core Group”, and the “Let’s Hack Together” event.

The **Model Core Group** started to discuss the identified features and tentative modules of the Model. In this working group, consortium actors interested in participating were able to exchange insights on the Model to develop it together. Two of these working sessions were held in Catalonia on June 26 and July 10, 2023, counting **15 and 13 attendees** respectively.

³ Data: 4290 inhabitants; Share of under-18s: 19.9 % [Hamburg average: 16.6 %], Proportion of over 64-year-olds: 9.4% [Hamburg average: 18.0%, Percentage of foreigners: 45.2 % [Hamburg average: 17.7 %], Unemployment rate: 11.2 % [Hamburg average: 6.4 %], The average income per taxpayer in Veddel is €15,831 per year (2013), the overall Hamburg average is €39,054. More information at: <https://www.hamburg-travel.com/discover-hamburg/areas/wilhelmsburg-veddel/>

Figure 10 - Online session from the Model Core Group.

Regarding the Model Core Group platform section, participants could share documents, insights and the possibility of having a conversation, so that co-creation was collected in the same place for later consultation.

In spring 2024, two additional online Core Model working sessions were conducted at an interregional level, involving participants from all three INTEGER regions. The first session included the INTEGER partners, while the second brought together key stakeholders from each region.

Figure 11 - The Model Core group on the Glocal.network platform.

The first **Key stakeholder pre-event** on April 18, 2023, involved **39 participants** from Krakow, Catalonia, and Hamburg who discussed the challenges of the INTEGER project and its model implementation. Key challenges identified included developing the potential of older adults, improving transparency and communication between 4H organisations, and aligning actions to enhance the quality of life.

Prior to the online pre-event, the key stakeholders were invited to complete a short Google form to identify a healthy living and well-being challenge in their region. This initiative aimed to foster stakeholder engagement, assess their profiles, including sector and region, and pinpoint the main regional challenge based on topics identified during the INTEGER partner study visits.

The first session of Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! was held on May 17, 2023. This event gathered online **40 participants** from academia, public entities, large companies,

SMEs, and social organisations, and addressed inter-regionally the three challenges identified in the pre-event. They worked in smaller inter-regional and intersectoral groups to reflect on innovative solutions, and share experiences and best practices.

This event had a follow-up **event** on May 25, 2023, where **40 participants** engaged in thoughtful discussions to share best practices and address key questions. In total, 41 participants attended across both sessions. Another objective of session 2 was to reach a solution to support the social innovators to reach the market with solutions to challenges that the ecosystem struggled with, at a regional level but at a transnational level as well. The promotion of live discussion in breakout rooms during session 2 enabled the follow-up of the discussions initiated in session 1 and enabled networking.

Another interregional event was the webinar titled "**Col-laber Training Day**" facilitated by AFEdeMy on April 19, 2024. This event aimed to strengthen collaboration between different actors within European innovation ecosystems. A total of **43 participants** from various quadruple helix sectors—Industry (5), Academia (21), Government (10), and Civil Society (3) and unknown (4) - attended.

During the session, participants learned about the essential fundamentals and skills required for Col-labers. These include social innovation, digital skills, networking capabilities, and the ability to boost collaborations within and across regional ecosystems.

The training session featured Antonius Schröder from ESSI (European School of Social Innovation) and Laia Pascual from Ship2B. Key topics such as social innovation and project management were also covered. Additionally, the Glocal.network platform was presented as a community platform with active individuals from quadruple helix sectors.

3.3 Create and enact prototypes to improve the situation

One activity to disseminate the community EU-wide and incentivise a strong commitment from various organisations was the official launch of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Wellbeing. To expand the INTEGER community regionally, Col-laborathons have been held in the three regions, serving as mechanisms to integrate social innovation actors into the regional innovation ecosystem using the INTEGER 4 H Model.

*Tailored to the new generation of living labs, **Col-laborathons** are dynamic platforms that operationalize quadruple helix collaboration. These events unite actors from academia, industry, government, and civil society to work together on specific challenges, such as nutrition and healthy living or social inclusion. By fostering interdisciplinary cooperation, Col-laborathons aim to develop innovative solutions to pressing societal issues.*

Official launch of the Col-laboratory

The OpenLivingLab Days was the stage chosen to officially launch the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory. This flagship annual event organised by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) took place in September 2023 and attracted over 200 participants, giving INTEGER

actions visibility, reaching a wider audience and credibility, in the context of such prestigious and recognised events.

To support this initiative, a Terms of Reference document was created and made available [here](#) (recently updated), to gather signatures and endorsements from stakeholders. Signatures have been collected through, firstly a google form, and updated to an EU Survey, an online survey-management system designed to create and publish globally accessible and GDPR-compliant forms. The survey can be accessed through [here](https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EUINTEGERCollaboratorySurvey2024): <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EUINTEGERCollaboratorySurvey2024> and has been shared at INTEGER initiatives.

The Public Signature of the Terms of Reference (ToR) brought together influential organisations from the 4 Helix, demonstrating their commitment to co-creating innovative solutions for societal challenges and validating our solution. The list of signatories can be found in Annex 2.

The membership form is being shared and disseminated by all consortium partners to expand the community and increase participation in the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory and in the Glocal.network platform.

Regional and Interregional Col-laborathons

The **Col-laborathons** across Catalonia, Krakow, and Hamburg are unique, reflecting each region's contextual needs and opportunities. In each event participants were invited to present or collaborate on health and well-being topics, solutions and implemented actions, culminating in the selection of a winner for the regional col-laborathon, who would then advance to the grand finale. The common evaluation criteria used were Concept & Innovation, Sustainability & Replicability, and Impact. Detailed information about these initiatives can be found in *Deliverable 2.2 - Col.laborathon Report & Exploitation Plan*.

- **Catalonia** event took place in Tarragona, Spain, on November 22, 2023, with **55 participants**. Following a session that presented challenges and local use cases, experts and participants formed diverse groups to tackle the "Health and Wellness for Life" challenge. Key activities included co-creation workshops and focus group discussions aimed at amplifying the INTEGER 4 Helix collaborative framework's impact. Key presentations were delivered by Adrià Buzón Lausín of Cuideo® on "From Economic Benefit to Social Impact: Business Strategies With Real Social Impact" and Maite Fibla Gasparin from Ship2B Ventures, who provided insights on innovative financing and incorporating Sustainable Development Goals into business agendas. Specialised training sessions empowered attendees with skills for presenting projects to investors, emphasising social impact and growth potential. The event culminated in a **pitch contest** where **six projects** in different development phases were highlighted. **Health Cities Generator** project, from Bax & Company, was the winner.
- **Krakow** event was organised by Krakow Technology Park and Jagiellonian University, in collaboration with the Life Science Krakow Cluster, and took place from November 29 to December 1, 2023, with **over 200 participants**. **Five teams**, consisting of 4 to 7 people each, worked on their ideas for three days, culminating in final pitches before a wide audience

on the third day. The winning project, **SąsiadeX**, was selected alongside four other equal prize winners. All teams received financial rewards, with the winning team also offered dedicated mentoring and implementation opportunities. On June 13-14, 2024, the Krakow Technology Park hosted the **second edition of AHathon** – Active Healthy Ageing Hackathon, dedicated to creating innovative solutions for older adults. The event attracted **51 participants** from academia, business, startups, and older adults, who collaborated to address contemporary challenges faced by older adults. The participants formed **eight groups** and worked intensively for two days, supported by 14 mentors from various fields. A jury of four members, representing Krakow Technology Park, LifeScience Krakow Cluster, 3 PG, and the Krakow City Hall, evaluated the projects. The **EDISONDA** team won the grand prize for their systemic approach to medication management. The winners will also join the mentorship program.

- **Hamburg** col-laborathon was divided into two workshops and two start-up pitches on October 11 and November 22, 2023, with **27 participants** (21 from public administration, economy, university, civil society, and 6 start-ups). The event started with inputs about federal and state initiatives on social innovation, followed by best practice presentations by Living Lab representatives from Bremen, Siegen, and Barcelona. **Six start-up companies** presented their innovative health solutions, evaluated by a jury consisting of Kai Schnackenberg, Kai Fritze, and Marcus Falke. The winner was **the start-up company HELP Mee**, represented by Annika Bruhns-Petersson and Antje Kallweit, which is creating an innovative app to help citizens deal with pain through a specialised therapy. The event concluded with discussions on the next steps, including regular digital and in-person meetings, agreement on short and medium-term goals and milestones, and the creation of a joint roadmap. Participants were encouraged to subscribe to the Glocal.network platform for further cooperation work.

The **EU INTEGER Col-laborathon** was the culmination of the regional events. Held online on January 17, 2024, and with **28 participants**, it brought together the winning projects from each region along with additional stakeholders. The event featured presentations on the outcomes of the regional col-laborathons, an inspirational talk on financing strategies with Josep Biosca of the SHIP2B Foundation, and pitches from the highest-ranked proposals across the regions. The final winner was announced during the event, and the INTEGER team awarded the winner's label and accolades to the finalists underscoring their dedication to fostering development and fundraising support.

3.4 Evaluate and reflect on action to learn and iterate

Besides the activities already developed by the project, as part of *Task 5.2 on Stakeholder engagement and liaison with relevant initiatives*, SHINE is developing a **learning network**. This tool features a new section where partners can share documents, reports, research, and available digital tools within the platform. Bi-weekly question prompts will also drive conversations to enhance participation and engagement. The learning network is scheduled for launch in September and mainly aims to foster engagement of the participants in the platform.

Moreover, an **exploratory session** was held in July 2024, involving stakeholders from the quadruple helix. The primary objective was to engage these stakeholders and encourage their integration into the EU Col-laboratory. They were also invited to the upcoming webinar aimed at showcasing their work, emphasising the importance of win-win relationships for effective engagement. The updated agenda and the list of participants in the webinar will be reported in Deliverable 5.2.

A **webinar with sister projects** of INTEGER is scheduled for September 16, 2024, from 12:00 to 13:30 CET. Participants include:

- INTEGER - Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions (Rafel Nualart, Fàtima Canseco-López)⁴
- CHEAD - Change Hubs for Ecosystemic Social Solutions (Marco Traversi, Dana Cappiello)⁵
- IBESI - Integrated Baltic Ecosystem for Social Innovation (Mart Veliste, Merey Beisembayev)⁶
- POSITIVE - Participatory Open Social Innovation Through Interlinking Valuable Ecosystems (Clara Duffner)⁷
- CONSOLID8 - Consolidating Deep & Inclusive Social Innovation Ecosystems (Raluca Prelucă)⁸
- SIRENE - Social Innovation Responsive Environments NETWORK (Carina Dantas)⁹

This webinar aims to foster synergies among sister projects and will feature a co-creation session to define the next steps for the EU-wide INTEGER community. The webinar will be recorded and added to the INTEGER website and on the Glocal.network platform.

Efforts on **communication and dissemination** will also be pursued. One highlight goes to the presentation of the INTEGER project in the final event of [NET4Age-Friendly](#) (COST Action that counts approximately 700 members around the world, related to health and well-being). Additionally, INTEGER will be featured in a panel discussion with representatives from the three regional innovation ecosystems at the [Hamburg Innovation Summit](#), in September 2024. Each regional partner will present a summary highlighting their respective innovation ecosystem. The Col-laboration winner, the Healthy Cities Generator (HCG), was also given the opportunity to present their project and connect with potential “partners”. Moreover, the final version of the 4H INTEGER Model will be presented at the [OpenLivingLab Days 2024](#), scheduled for September 2024 in Timisoara. This aims to generate interest among this network around the INTEGER project, possibly create synergies, and invite more people to the community.

⁴ GA number: 101096563; website: <https://integercollab.eu/>

⁵ GA number: 10052454; website: <https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=10052454>

⁶ GA number: 101096680; website: <https://bia.ee/ibesi/>

⁷ GA number: 101096390 ; website: <https://www.trentinoinnovation.eu/en/progetto/positive-participatory-open-social-innovation-through-interlinking-valuable-ecosystems-en/>

⁸ GA number: 101096781; website: <https://www.consolid8.ro/ecosystem/deep-inclusive-social-innovation-ecosystems>

⁹ GA number: 101096077; website: <https://sireneproject.eu/>

The EU Col-laboratory was also enhanced on the website, by including it in the homepage (see Figure 12).

Figure 12 - Screenshot of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory highlighted on the homepage of the INTEGER website

Catalonia, Krakow, and Hamburg are also planning to create **more activities** to attract additional participants and further engage those already involved.

The **mentorship program**, initiated in March 2024 as part of Task 3.3, focuses on supporting winners from regional Col-laborathons through incubation, acceleration, and collaborative learning. The program aims to ensure that social innovation projects achieve economic sustainability without public funding. Mentors guide participants in strategic planning, innovation, and market alignment, with monthly and biweekly meetings providing ongoing support.

In Catalonia, biweekly online sessions offer consistent development support using established methodologies. The first phase in Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia revealed region-specific mentoring models. Krakow emphasised design thinking and Agile methods, Hamburg focused on networking and social entrepreneurship, and Catalonia centred on incubating social-digital projects.

The program encourages cross-regional collaboration through events and training sessions, enhancing effectiveness. Despite regional diversity, there is a recognised need for greater alignment to maximize impact. Overall, the mentorship process creates a supportive environment, enabling participants to innovate, overcome challenges, and achieve long-term success.

During all project phases, **dissemination and communication activities** have been pursued.

4 Newsletters have been distributed and disseminated through at least 700 stakeholders of the NET4AgeFriendly network, through email, and also on the INTEGER website, INTEGER social media and partners' websites. The recent newsletters emphasised efforts to join the Glocal.platform and sign the Terms of Reference (see Figure 13 and Figure 14).

Newsletter #2 | September 2023

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

INTEGER: IN THE SPOTLIGHT

EU INTEGER COLLABORATORY UNVEILED:

The EU INTEGER Collaboratory project aims to foster collaboration among individuals and institutions from the quadruple helix in regional innovation ecosystems. This initiative responds to the critical need for stronger connections between regions and actors to maximise the potential of EU innovations.

In a historic moment that promises to redefine innovation and collaboration in the realm of health and wellbeing, the EU INTEGER Collaboratory was officially launched during the #OpenLivingLab Days, that happened last September 23. [You can read more about it here.](#)

JOIN THE SUSTAINABILITY AND INNOVATION MOVEMENT!

Discover the power of sustainability and social innovation by becoming a member of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Wellbeing. If you are passionate about creating positive change and driving innovation in health and wellbeing, here's your chance to be part of a transformative community. Simply fill out the [form](#) and read the [Terms of Reference](#) to embark on this exciting journey of co-creation and innovation.

Figure 13 - Promotion of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory in project newsletter #2

Figure 14 - Promotion of the INTEGER platform in project newsletter #3

Several **LinkedIn posts** on the INTEGER account (384 followers) have been made, to attract continuous interest from the followers. Specifically, an average of one post per week has been published, totalling 88 posts by the end of August 2024. A focus on the project platform has also been made, to increase the number of people involved there (see Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Examples of LinkedIn posts promoting the INTEGER platform

The **platform** has been continuously enriched with content and various engagement strategies. In the "Discover" section, participants can find numerous news articles related to recent social innovation events, project updates, and health and well-being developments. These articles are typically contributed by partners, but all platform participants are encouraged to post. In the "Connect" section, users can browse and contact all registered individuals and organisations, utilising the detailed profiles available. The "Participate" section hosts projects where everyone can collaborate via chat and shared documents. This includes the "Col-labers Corner" and the learning network. Materials for the mentorship sessions, developed as part of Task 3.3, will also be made available on the platform to foster communication and collaboration among team members.

Additionally, the project has been orally presented at several **conferences** to promote INTEGER and expand its community. These include, among others:

1. 21st European Week of Regions and Cities held in Brussels on October 11, 2023. In this event, a participatory lab was held exploring European perspectives on promoting entrepreneurial and social innovation skills to boost innovation and development that

leave no one behind. The event was co-hosted by the organisations UNITEE (Belgium), SHINE 2Europe (Portugal), Friends of Europe (Belgium), Eurochambres (Belgium), AFEdemy (the Netherlands), and i2CAT Foundation (Spain), along with the EU-funded projects SIRENE, NET4Age.Friendly and INTEGER. As a result, a document with the results was prepared - <https://shine2.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/EU-Regions-Week.pdf>.

2. International Conference on Building Sustainable and Participatory Environments in Porto, Portugal, on May 7, 2024. In this event participated experts from areas revolving around SHAFE – Smart Healthy Age-Friendly Environments – to keep societal priorities at the top of the political agenda, by empowering ecosystems to promote independent living, green behaviours and inclusive practices, connecting all stakeholders to build sustainable and participatory environments.
3. 31st APDR Congress in Leiria, Portugal, on June 27, 2024. The presentation, titled “INTEGER: Fostering Social-Business Collaboration for Impactful Change,” highlighted the development of an EU-wide INTEGER innovative community.

Figure 16 - Presentation of the INTEGER project at the International Conference on Sustainable and Participatory Environments (Porto, Portugal, 2024)

The infographic below (Figure 17) summarises the methodology just presented with correspondence from each phase to the activities related.

Figure 17 - INTEGER activities that contributed to the constitution of the EU-wide INTEGER innovative community

While there is still a need to continue efforts to improve participant engagement on the platform and expand the EU-wide community, it is gratifying to note that the majority of participants in the events, whether online or in person, have expressed positive feedback and enthusiasm. A detailed analysis of the individuals and organisations involved, categorised by the type of 4H, will be provided in greater detail in Deliverable 5.2 (Stakeholder Liaison with Relevant Initiatives and Impact Monitoring Report) and Deliverable 5.3 (Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholder Implementation Report).

4 Sustainability of the EU-wide INTEGER innovative community

One of the key challenges faced is ensuring the sustainability of the EU-wide community on Health and Wellbeing beyond the project duration. To maintain the community alive, two main strategies have been identified:

1. Collaboration with established structures: partnering with existing entities that will continue beyond the project's lifespan, such as the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL) and the European School of Social Innovation (ESSI).
2. Utilisation of an independent platform: using a platform to connect all 4H stakeholders that is self-sustaining and not dependent on additional funding.

An agreement document will be drafted to formalise collaboration between INTEGER and ENOLL and/or ESSI, including placing a link to the INTEGER platform on their respective websites. Currently the INTEGER platform is hosted on the Glocal.network platform, however the consortium has explored other possible options to ensure sustainability post-project. This analysis considers which features are most beneficial for platform users by examining the most frequently used elements in the current version. After analysis, migrating content to a non-commercial, open-source platform with active stakeholder engagement, emerged as the most viable approach, even when considering the risks involved in the change. Plans include transferring Glocal.network platform content to this new platform and organising an end-of-project event to explain the change, justify the migration and promote its adoption with the goal of integrating all stakeholders that are presently in our platform and attracting others.

During the last months, different options have been considered that are listed below:

1. **TheGlocalNetWork**: This option considers the continuity of the current platform. However, an analysis should be done to understand how the community could cover the maintenance expenses.
2. **SIRENE - Social Innovation Responsive Environments NETwork**. SIRENE is a Horizon Europe project from the same call as INTEGER and aims to support the growth of social innovation actors in eco-friendly and sustainable community-based services for SHAFE (Smart Healthy Age-Friendly Environments) implementation in Europe, by providing a workable framework for investment.

Considerations:

- SIRENE has an open-source [platform](#) free of charge currently under development by SHINE. Its property will be transferred to the [SHAFE Foundation](#). Willeke, director of AFEdemy, and Carina, CEO of SHINE, are the directors of SHAFE.
- SHINE and AFEdemy are two partners from the current INTEGER project.

- It could be possible to create different levels of administrators in order to dynamize the community but right now this option does not exist.
- The community has limited features. It is mainly made to contact people and share documents in an easy way.
- It does not allow to create tasks to follow and calendars.
- It is not possible to sign in at the community if not accepted by the administrator.
- At this point, INTEGER consortium cannot have access to the community.
- SIRENE platform has no similar features and characteristics as the Glocal.network platform, being a simpler option.

3. [EEN - European Enterprise Network](#). The world's largest support network for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with international ambitions.

The Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) helps businesses innovate and grow on an international scale. It is the world's largest support network for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with international ambitions.

The Network is active worldwide. It brings together experts from member organisations that are renowned for their excellence in business support.

Member organisations include:

- Chambers of commerce and industry
- Regional development organisations
- Universities and research institutes
- Innovation agencies

Individual businesses cannot become Network members, but they can enjoy the many services offered. Teams of Network experts in each member organisation offer personalised services to businesses. They know the local business environment and have contacts for business opportunities worldwide.

The Enterprise Europe Network can also offer a targeted approach aimed specifically at your business sector. Its groups of experts cover all key economic sectors, from healthcare, agri-food and intelligent energy to fashion and textile. In addition, the Network will help companies increase their resilience and support SMEs in their transition to more sustainable and digital business models.

For information and advice, [find a local Network contact point](#) in your region.

Figure 18 - EEN map. Retrieved from: <https://een.ec.europa.eu/news/een-annual-conference-2023-concludes>

Considerations:

- It is mainly a marketplace.
 - Besides it is business oriented it could be an opportunity to integrate/combine with the INTEGER social perspective.
 - An online meeting was held on July 18, 2024, with the Hamburg representative of the platform in order to know the “platform” details and evaluate possibilities.
 - At the [Partnering Opportunities](#) section it is possible to apply some filters and to find EU stakeholders within different fields.
4. **Decidem.** [Decidim.org](#) is a free open-source platform that enables organisations and institutions to initiate participatory processes like deliberation, decision making, collaboration and co-design. It can be used, copied, modified or shared with any kind of organisation, no matter its scale. Thanks to that, more than 300 cities and organisations around the world now use Decidim.

Figure 19 - Available languages at the Decidim platform

Considerations:

- This platform is open source and free of charge.
- All platform features are reported [here](#).
- In case this platform is chosen, there are two different possibilities:
 - To create a specific Decidim for INTEGER. It will be necessary to define a front UX which has an approximate cost of 1.500,00 euros depending on how much customised UI the INTEGER consortium decides to have.
 - To build an INTEGER “section” within the Catalonia Col-laboratory Decidim. In this case possible UX definition expenses could be really low or free of Charge. This option could create several misunderstandings for members outside Catalonia.

5. [AccelUP](#) is a platform developed by [ENOLL](#) and used by the [Vitalise](#) project. This project aims to open up Living Lab research infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the health and wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond, by enabling personal Transnational Access to [17 Living Lab research infrastructures](#) and by supporting remote digital access to datasets of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday living environments through harmonised processes and common tools. The AccelUP platform allows innovative people and accredited suppliers to get in touch to raise challenges, do tests, etc, through the different Living Labs. The proposal is to merge both or link one to the other, but in this second case this would imply that INTEGER would have migrated to another place to then make this link.

To keep the community vibrant and engaged, maintaining contact and sharing space is essential. The shared space must enable members to connect with others within their region - whether in Hamburg, Krakow, or beyond - nurturing local and global interactions.

The current digital platform, the Glocal.network, served this purpose, fostering a sense of community and promoting a collaborative, innovation-driven working philosophy.

SIRENE platform has emerged as a promising option, due to its alignment with the INTEGER philosophy and the familiarity of some members who are already actively engaged in the INTEGER project.

In the coming weeks, the INTEGER consortium will decide on the most suitable platform to transition to, ensuring it supports the community's growth and enhances communication and collaboration opportunities. Once a decision is made, a careful plan will be developed and executed to migrate the content from the current platform to the new one, ensuring a smooth transition and proper setup.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The EU-wide INTEGER innovative community brings together participants from the three regional innovation ecosystems - Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia - alongside key stakeholders from the quadruple helix, all focused on advancing health and well-being across various regions and countries.

Currently, we have involved several persons and organisations from the three regions and beyond, with 190 participants registered on the Glocal.network platform (see Annex 3). Key stakeholders from related EU projects or institutions include NET4AgeFriendly, SIRENE, SHAFE, FoodCLIC, FORGING, VITALISE, EcoADAPT50, SMART CIRCUIT, ESSI, ENoLL, VIU, AICS, Ministry of Health Government of Catalonia, AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster, SARGIM Foundation, IASP.

Activities like the regional Col-laborathons or the online Col-laber Training Day received strong participation and highly positive feedback from attendees, largely due to the support provided by the juries and the subsequent mentorships. Additionally, the co-creation elements, such as those in the Core Model group and key stakeholder events, were also well-received by stakeholders.

The ongoing incubation and acceleration activities play a crucial role in expanding, strengthening, and consolidating the INTEGER community, fostering a strong sense of belonging among its members. Participants recognise that the INTEGER project, through its diverse activities, methodologies, and underlying philosophy, significantly supports the advancement of their MVPs and projects. It also facilitates valuable connections with peers within their own EU regions and beyond.

Collaborative actions with a focus on social impact and ethical business practices are becoming increasingly common and in demand across the EU. Organizations and individuals involved are showing greater sensitivity and commitment to these values, further amplifying INTEGER's reach and influence. This collective effort is instrumental in growing the INTEGER community and spreading the project's impact across Europe.

The project is actively planning activities to expand and deepen community engagement, including a webinar in September featuring a co-creation session on strengthening the EU-wide INTEGER community. A systemic design approach will guide these efforts, aiming to maximise impact.

To ensure sustainability beyond the project's duration, discussions with ENoLL and ESSI will be scheduled to explore collaborative opportunities. Additionally, a transition to an open-source platform is foreseen. To mitigate the risk of losing participants, an online event will be organised for all participants to showcase the advantages of this new platform, complemented by a dissemination campaign.

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7 Annex 1

Table 2 - 4H stakeholders identified in the innovation ecosystem of Catalonia

Catalonia		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Type of Stakeholder
Government	Regional	Eurecat
		Health department - Catalanian government
Civil Society	Local	Associació de pacients
		Consell Català de la gent gran
		Association of "AMPA" Mothers and fathers of primary schools
		Neighbourhood associations
Academia	Regional	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
		Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV)
		Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
		Universitat Barcelona (UB)

Table 3 - 4H stakeholders identified in the innovation ecosystem of Krakow

Krakow		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Government	National	The Polish Ministry of Health
	Regional	Marshall Office of Malopolska Region
	Local	Municipality Centre of Social Assistance
Civil Society	National	Polish National Initiative for Collaboration of Senior Councils
	Regional	Krakow Smog Alert
	Local	Senior Activity Centres
Industry	National	Polish Confederation Lewiatan
	Regional	Klaster Lifescience
	Local	DIABMED
Academia	National	Polish National Gerontological Association
	Regional	University of Science and technology Krakow
	Local	Faber Education Centre

Table 4 - 4H stakeholders identified in the innovation ecosystem of Hamburg

Hamburg		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Government	Regional	Hamburger Investitions und Förderbank
		Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg (+Industry)

		Arbeitskreis nachhaltige Stadtgesundheit (+Civil Society, Academia)
Industry	National	Aidhere
Academia	Regional	University Hospital Hamburg

Table 5 - 4H stakeholders identified in European innovation ecosystem

International Stakeholders	
4 H areas	Stakeholder
Government	DG Employment & Social inclusion
Civil Society	Age platform Europe
Industry	European Business & innovation Network
	Phillips Health innovation port ; Gaia AG
Academia	Una Europa
	NET4Age COST action

8 Annex 2

Hand signatories during the OLLD in September 2023

Name	Position	Signature
Manel Balcells	Catalan Ministry of Health, Government of Catalonia, Minister for Health	
Sergi Marcen	Secretary of Telecommunications and Digital Transformation, Government of Catalonia	
Kai Schnackenber	Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg; Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs and Integration. Deputy head of division for international affairs and innovation	
Ramon Maspons	Catalan Ministry of Health, Government of Catalonia, Chief Health Innovation Strategist	
Natalia Bursiewicz	Krakov Technology Park, Vice President of the Board	
Sergi Figuerola	i2Cat Foundation, Chief Technology and Innovation Officer, CTO @5GBarcelona	
Alba De Martino Rodriguez	Aragonese Institute of Health Sciences (IACS), Knowledge and Innovation Production Area, Director	
Xavier Càmara	Universitat Rovira i Virgili URV, Business Management Department director	

José Martí	Valencian International University (VIU): (Vice-Rector for Research and Knowledge Transfer)	
Jaisiel Madrid	AMBIT – Living Spaces Cluster, Interiors Living Lab Manager	
Rosina Malagrida	IrsiCaixa AIDS Research Institute, Head of the Living Lab for Health	
Xavier Pérez	Fundación AEMA, Secretary	
Jürgen Howaldt	Chair of ESSI (European School of Social Innovation)	
Evdokimos Konstantinidis	European Network of Living Labs., Leader of ASOSS Research Group at Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Lab, President of ENoLL, Project Coordinator VITALISE H2020, Project Coordinator RAISE HE.	
Toñi Caro	INTEGER's coordinator and National Appointed Representative in the Managing Committee. INTEGER / Net4AgeFriendly - International Interdisciplinary Network on Health and Wellbeing	

Some other institutions that digitally confirm the support to this INTEGER project and document

- AFEdeMy
- F6S
- Krakow Technology Park
- Krakowia Jagiellonian University, Center for Evaluation and Analysis of Public Policies
- SHINE 2Europe
- Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili
- Memima baby
- Suara Cooperativa
- Living Lab Universidad de la Sabana
- EKA University of Applied Sciences
- Abdullah Gül University and Wellbeing Association

Figure 20 - List of signatories of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory during the OpenLivingLab Days event (September 2023).

9 Annex 3

Figure 21 - Analytics screenshots from the Glocal.network platform (August 29, 2024): General analysis

Figure 22 - Analytics screenshots from the Glocal.network platform (August 29, 2024): Users analysis

Figure 23 - Analytics screenshots from the Glocal.network platform (August 29, 2024): Conversations analysis